

MANAGEMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11090377>

Abstract. *In this article, the essence of the principles, methodological approaches and mechanisms of preschool educational organization management is presented.*

Keywords: *management, flexibility, inclusiveness, the principle of integrity, the principle of systematicity, technology, innovation, innovative approach.*

УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ДОШКОЛЬНОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЕЙ И МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена сущность принципов, методических подходов и механизмов управления дошкольной образовательной организацией.*

Ключевые слова: *менеджмент, гибкость, инклюзивность, принцип честности, принцип системности, технологии, инновации, инновационный подход.*

We analyze methodological approaches to management. Methodical approaches to the management of a preschool educational organization are the basis for the development and implementation of a management strategy that is adapted to the characteristics of working with preschool children and reflects modern trends in the field of education and management.

A situational approach that includes flexible management based on specific conditions and situations. A situational approach to the management of a preschool educational organization allows leaders to adapt to changing conditions and choose the most appropriate management decisions depending on the specific situation. This approach requires principals to have a deep understanding of both the internal dynamics of the organization and the external educational and social environment. Using a situational approach will help you manage more flexibly and effectively, allowing you to quickly respond to challenges and take advantage of opportunities that arise to grow your organization.

A process approach aimed at optimizing management and educational processes. The process approach is aimed at structuring and optimizing all management and training processes in the organization. The main focus is on continuous improvement of planning, organization, motivation and control processes, including identification of key processes, their analysis, modeling and optimization. The process approach makes it possible to achieve a high level of coordination of the actions of employees and increase the efficiency of management of the organization's resources.

Competency-based approach aimed at developing professional and personal competencies of employees. Competency-based approach emphasizes the importance of developing professional and personal competencies of leaders and all employees of preschool education organization. The main focus is not only on acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills, but also on developing independent problem solving, critical thinking, creativity and social

adaptation skills. Using a competency-based approach helps build a motivated, professionally trained and effective team capable of implementing innovative educational programs and projects.

According to the competence-based approach, the concept of "competence" is the generalized ability to solve professional problems in a certain field due to knowledge, skills, and experience.

The idea of personal and professional development of the head of the educational institution is the basis of the personal development approach, in which the internal environment of the person, his activity, the need for self-awareness are the factors of development.

Methodological approaches to the management of a preschool educational organization determine the methods and tools for the implementation of management tasks. (to figure 1)

Figure 1. Methodical approaches to managing a preschool educational organization

To justify the personal development approach, LMMitina defines the following three main areas of professional development of a person:

- content (the content of the professional development process: development of conceptual and technological models of personal development);
- dynamic (temporary field of skill improvement for a creative person through the stage of independent and conscious career choice);
- the institution of professional development of a person, including the type of society in which the "professional market" operates, educational systems and specific social groups in which the development process is carried out".

Applying these approaches to the practice of managing a preschool education organization requires the leader not only high professional knowledge and skills, but also a deep

understanding of the peculiarities of preschool education, as well as the ability to build effective relationships. both within the organization and with the external environment.

NM Kvasnikova's dissertation focuses on the importance of innovative activities of educational organizations in their development and compliance with high standards of the time. Particular attention is paid to the mechanism of personal competence development of principals, which is the main factor of successful management of innovative activities in pre-school education and general education organizations. The author states: "The research hypothesis is based on the assumption that the implemented mechanisms of managing innovative activities at the innovation stage ensure the effectiveness of transformations, if... the head of an educational organization has advanced preparation for managing innovative activities, which allows the implementation of effective mechanisms of managing complex transformations."

of VN Kazakova, dedicated to the management of innovative activities in preschool and general educational organizations, the author focuses on the relevance of developing and introducing innovative approaches in the field of education. A distinctive feature of this research is an in-depth analysis of the mechanism of personal competence development of principals to improve management processes in preschool educational organizations. The author states: "The current socio-economic situation in the country has convincingly shown that there is an urgent need to fundamentally change the management of the education system, which has made the use of the internal resources of the system more urgent."

TP Morozova's dissertation on the pedagogical foundations of managing the development of preschool educational organization focuses on the importance of the integration of management theory and educational sciences. The author states that the management system is a hierarchical structure of interrelated processes aimed at achieving quality results.

ANMorozova's thesis "Management of methodical work on the basis of diagnostics in preschool education organization" is aimed at developing and implementing a comprehensive approach to management of methodical work in preschool education. The author emphasizes that modern changes in the education system require new approaches to the management of pre-school educational organizations, in which individualization of the educational process, adaptation to the needs and interests of children play a key role. Morozova emphasizes the need to use a diagnostic approach that allows to optimize the pedagogical process, increase its quality and efficiency in methodical work.

Based on the scientific analysis carried out in this way, we believe that the director should have the following qualities in the development of personal competencies in managing a preschool education organization:

1. Leadership qualities: It was found that the director's leadership qualities have a decisive influence on the effectiveness of preschool educational organizations, on creating a favorable environment for development and learning.

2. The role of communication skills: the importance of improved communication skills for successful collaboration with staff, parents and children has been confirmed, helping to increase overall satisfaction among stakeholders.

3. The need for an innovative approach: an innovative approach and readiness to introduce new methods and technologies into the educational process are important in ensuring the competitiveness and quality of education.

4. The importance of management skills: the presence and development of management skills is necessary for the effective organization of the work of a preschool educational organization, planning of its development and management of resources.

5. Importance of professional development: Continuous professional and personal development of principals is of great importance to adapt to changing conditions and demands in the field of early childhood education.

6. Effectiveness of the support and feedback system: the need to create support systems for directors, including feedback, mentoring and coaching as a means of improving their management and personal competencies, was identified.

In our research, not the qualities of the leader are studied, but the part that is directly used in the process of management activities and ensures its efficiency and the achievement of planned results.

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